

Case report

Unruptured primary ovarian pregnancy: a case report highlighting diagnostic challenges in Africa

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Abstract

The current study reports a delayed diagnosis of unruptured primary ovarian pregnancy (POP) in the first trimester and identifies potential contributing factors to the low rate of preoperative POP diagnosis in Africa. **Case summary.** She was a 24-year-old unbooked G4 P 3+ 1 2A Nigerian housewife with ruptured ovarian pregnancy. She had a Clinic visit four weeks earlier with a positive urinary pregnancy test and USS report that suggested PID with an empty, normal-sized uterus, significant free fluid in POD, and free adnexa. She presented with features of acute abdomen with background amenorrhoea. At the index presentation, she was afebrile, anicteric, and not pale. The pulse rate was 84bpm and blood pressure was 110/80mmHg. The abdomen was full and minimally moved with respiration. There was lower abdominal tenderness, rigidity, and guarding. Vaginal examination revealed normal female external genitalia, no evidence of bleeding, the cervix was posterior, and the Os closed. There was bilateral fullness of the pouch of Douglas (POD), and cervical motion tenderness was positive. Haemoglobin concentration was 10.2g/dl. Transvaginal sonography showed a normal-sized uterus, empty endometrium, a mixed echogenic structure with solid and cystic components measuring 4.4cm x 5.2cm in the right adnexium, and an intra-abdominal fluid collection. She had an emergency laparotomy with right Salpingo-oophorectomy. The specimen showed an ovarian tissue demarcating a cavity with haemorrhage, chorionic villi, isolated trophoblastic cells, and sheets of decidualized cells. The adhered ipsilateral Fallopian tube was grossly intact. **Conclusion:** There was a plethora of mitigating factors that revealed the gaps in the prompt diagnosis of unruptured POP preoperatively in this patient. However, national recommendations of site localisation of gestational sac in the first trimester before routine ANC, uptake of transvaginal USS, and adoption of new criteria for USS for OP, together with a sensitive method of quantification of β -hCG, would have given an upper edge in this regard.

Keywords: Africa, Challenges, Preoperative diagnosis, Unruptured primary ovarian pregnancy.

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Introduction

Primary ovarian pregnancy (OP) is a rare form of non-tubal ectopic gestation where an ovum is fertilised and implanted primarily in the ovary.¹ OP is achieved via fertilisation and implantation of an ovum on the ovarian surfaces, from a ruptured or aborted tubal gestation, or from a fertilized ovum in the peritoneal cavity.² It accounts for about 0.5 - 3% of all ectopic pregnancies and constitutes 1/2,000 to 1/60,000 of all conceived pregnancies.³⁻⁵ In Africa, it does not readily get the required heedfulness.^{6,7,8} Early diagnosis of POP allows for conservative or medical treatment, preservation of healthy ovarian tissue, and future fertility.⁹ Traditional criteria by Otto Spiegelberg in 1878 for POP diagnosis¹⁰ which involves surgical and

histological assessments, focus more on postoperative diagnosis and are usually difficult to fulfil for preoperative diagnosis in a developing country like ours, particularly in rural settings with staggering health care delivery gaps.¹¹ On this account, there is a dire need for alternative pathways for preoperative diagnosis of POP.

The current study reports a delayed diagnosis of unruptured POP in the first trimester and also identifies the potential contributing factors to the low rate of preoperative POP diagnosis in Africa.

Case presentation

A 24 year-old unbooked G4 P 3+ 1 2A (last child birth: 2 years ago) Nigerian housewife presented at the gynaecological emergency unit of Federal University of Health Sciences Teaching Hospital Azare (FUHSTHA) with 8weeks amenorrhoea, 72 hours of severe sudden and recurrent lower abdominal pain (LAP), slight postcoital vaginal bleeding, and reports of positive pregnancy test (PT) and a two-day trans-abdominal ultrasonographic report of unruptured ectopic pregnancy from a peripheral health facility. However, there was no history of trauma, vomiting, abdominal distention, constipation, fever, fainting, dizziness, vaginal discharge, or urinary symptoms. Previous menstrual cycles were regular; she has had three terms of uncomplicated spontaneous vaginal deliveries, two were alive, and one had neonatal death from febrile illness. She was not on any form of contraceptives or drugs.

She had previously visited the general out-patient department of FUHSTHA four weeks earlier with a history of four weeks of amenorrhoea, slight LAP, catarrh, and a follow-up visit after two days with a positive urine pregnancy test (Beta Human Chorionic Gonadotropin, B-hCG) and trans-abdominal sonography report that suggested pelvic inflammatory disease (PID) with an empty normal-sized uterus, thickened endometrial echoplate measuring 1.5cm in AP diameter, significant free fluid in POD, and free adnexa. She had been commenced on antacids and haematinics, but symptoms persisted.

On examination, at the index presentation, she was afebrile (with axillary temperature 36.7 °C), anicteric, and not pale. The pulse rate was 84bpm and blood pressure was 110/80mmHg. The abdomen was full and minimally moved with respiration. There was lower abdominal tenderness, rigidity, and guarding, which preclude deep palpation. Vaginal examination revealed normal female external genitalia, no evidence of bleeding, the cervix was posterior, and the Os closed. There was bilateral fullness of the pouch of

Douglas (POD), and cervical motion tenderness was positive. Haemoglobin concentration was 10.2g/dl. Transvaginal sonography showed a normally sized uterus, empty endometrium, a mixed echogenic structure with solid and cystic components measuring 4.4cm x 5.2cm in the right adnexium, and an intra-abdominal fluid collection. She had an emergency explorative laparotomy with right Salpingo-oophorectomy on account of POP with right tubo-ovarian adhesion and uneventful postoperative recovery. Intraoperative findings included an empty and bulky uterus, an unremarkable left fallopian tube, 250ml of blood in the pelvic cavity, and a haemorrhagic mass in the right adnexium.

The Gross examination of the right Salpingo-oophorectomy specimen showed a dark brown tissue measuring 6x4x4cm; it weighed 40g, had haemorrhagic cut surfaces, a cavity containing amniotic fluid, and a developing embryo. The fallopian tube component of the specimen measured 4cm in length and 1cm in its widest diameter and had unremarkable cut surfaces.

Microscopic examination showed ovarian tissue demarcating a cavity with haemorrhage, chorionic villi, isolated trophoblastic cells, sheets of decidualized cells, and an unremarkable fallopian tube (Figure 1).

Fig.1(photomicrograph): 1a- Shows an ovarian stroma with cystic follicle demarcating a cavity with haemorrhage, chorionic villi, isolated trophoblastic cells, and sheets of decidualized cells (x40).

Discussion

Primary ovarian pregnancy (POP) is a rare extra-uterine gestation with an intricate diagnostic method involving clinical, surgical, radiological, and pathological assessments. The initial proposed parameters of diagnosis of POP by Otto Spiegelberg,⁹ incline towards post-operative diagnosis. These criteria are as follows: intact fallopian tube separate from the ovary on the involved side, the gestational sac in the normal position of the ovary, the ovary with the gestational sac connected to the uterus by the ovarian ligament, and the specimen having ovarian tissue attached to and in the wall of the gestational sac.⁹ These criteria require good health facilities with histological services. With staggering healthcare delivery gaps in our healthcare system, for example, the histological samples that require careful evaluation by pathologists and may not be taken for histology or the lack of such pathological services in our primary and secondary care centres,¹² there is a need to work out a preoperative diagnostic modalities rather than relying on a postoperative criteria proposed by Otto Spiegelberg over a century ago.

Fig. 1b- Shows an ovarian stroma with cystic follicle demarcating a cavity with haemorrhage, chorionic villi, isolated trophoblastic cells, and sheets of decidualized cells (x100).

The setbacks in the preoperative diagnosis of POP in Africa stem from its rarity, underestimation, unsuspecting clinical scenario, non-identifiable risk factors, absence of specific clinical features, and high rate of gynaecological mimics.^{13,14} POP may be misdiagnosed as other entities depending on the gestational age of the pregnancy: 75% of ovarian gestations may rupture in the early first trimester and are usually misdiagnosed as corpus luteal haemorrhage.¹⁵ It may also be misdiagnosed as a tubal pregnancy. [2] In this case report, LAP with positive PT on a follow-up visit, where trans-abdominal USS suggested PID may have turned the searchlight away from POP, which is quite rare in our environment. In the index case, it was mistaken as an early intrauterine gestation with the possibility of PID following positive PT, and an empty uterus with free fluid in the pouch of Douglas (POD) by trans-abdominal USS. On account of delayed presentation or diagnosis, POP has been carried unknowingly beyond the 40 weeks as an intrauterine pregnancy.^{16,17} This misdiagnosis is not without consequences: haemorrhage and potential shock in between hospital visits, [6-8] as occurred in this case, impaired fertility from rupture or surgical intervention, foetal death,¹⁶ or wrong intervention such as induction of labour which further compromises the health status of the patient.¹⁶

Significantly larger numbers of unbooked pregnancies in Africa, inadequate gynaecological emergency care, and a penchant for delay in seeking health care also impede early diagnosis.^{18,19} Symptoms of POP may start before the end of a regular menstrual cycle [20] and may be perceived as unrelated to pregnancy or may be interpreted as postcoital bleeding akin to the index case report. To address these, ultrasonography (preferably, transvaginal technique) with newer criteria must be consciously followed in all our gynaecological clinics. Unfortunately, in our region of the world, there is low uptake of transvaginal ultrasonography, particularly in early cyesis²¹, as well as a lack of national guidelines on the localisation of the site of implantation of an embryo before the commencement of routine ANC visits.²² Adoption of newer USS criteria together with more sensitive methods of quantification of serum β -hCG may give an edge in preoperative assessment of OP in our setting. Ultrasonography may detect gestational sacs at 5.5 to 6 weeks of gestation and beyond.²³ The gestational sac adjacent to the ovary in the first trimester is depicted as a double echogenic ring within a hypochoic adnexal mass, and the presence of ovarian cortex, including a

corpus luteum follicle, around the mass.^{24, 25} These findings were probably not present at the first USS in our case report, probably because of early gestation at 4 weeks. Surprisingly, this description is evidenced in the histology report postoperatively. (Figure1) In the second trimester and beyond, the ring sign becomes less useful [24, 26], but one key feature that remains accurate and constant, differentiating between ectopic and intrauterine pregnancies, is mantle distance, which is the thickness of the myometrium surrounding the gestational sac.²⁷ Lewiss et al, in their systematic review of ectopic pregnancies and ultrasound, document a cutoff point of <8 mm mantle distance for gynecologists working in emergency units to raise a high index of suspicion for ectopic pregnancy.²⁷ This is particularly paramount because of the flaws associated with USS. The errors associated with the USS are not just limited to the first trimester in localizing the site of gestation. Keller et al reported a missed 15-week tubo-ovarian pregnancy in the second trimester as intra-uterine on trans-abdominal ultrasound.²⁵ These lapses in USS underscore the need to consciously adopt mantle distance when localizing gestational age. However, the mantle distance was not calculated in our patient. Also, it is difficult to differentiate OP from haemorrhagic cysts such as corpus luteum by USS.²⁸ However, a wide echogenic ring with an internal echo lucent area on the ovarian surface, the presence of ovarian cortex, including corpus luteum or follicles around the mass, and the echogenicity of the ring usually greater than that of the ovary itself strongly favours POP.^{29,30}

It is important to emphasize that no single modality is the panacea to preoperative diagnosis of POP, but the conscious efforts and high index of suspicion in each case, as available diagnostic modalities are not without drawbacks. The diagnostic accuracy of clinical examinations, serum HCG concentrations, ultrasound, MRI imaging, or laparoscopy is limited,³¹ with the risk of misdiagnosis.³² HCG may be negative in some cases (2%).^{33, 34} Preoperative diagnosis could be as low as 8%,³⁵ relying largely on histopathological examination,³⁵ while intraoperative diagnostic yield could be as low as 28% due to the inability to differentiate POP from corpus luteum cysts and hemorrhagic cysts.³⁵ However, symptoms like lower abdominal pain, and transvaginal ultrasonography aid the diagnosis of POP in over 90% of preoperative diagnoses, which allows for conservative surgery and sparing of the ovary.³⁶

Conclusion

Although the index case met the Spiegelberg criteria for primary ovarian pregnancy, albeit post-operatively, pre-operative diagnosis remains elusive in most African settings like ours. It is hoped that with careful application of serum β -hCG, transvaginal ultrasound, and diagnostic laparoscopy on all women presenting with amenorrhoea, a positive pregnancy test, regardless of trans-abdominal USS report, will promptly improve the diagnosis of POP before it ruptures, with unpredictable sequelae. Furthermore, the national recommendation of site localization of gestational sac in the first trimester before routine ANC will be pivotal to achieving the above.

Declaration

Ethics approval and consent to participate.

The local institutional review board (IRB) was not required for anonymous case reports. There are no identifying images or other personal or clinical details of the patient that compromise anonymity in this manuscript.

Consent for publication

Informed oral consent for publication was obtained from the patient.

Availability of data and materials

Data will be made available upon written request to the corresponding author.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions

AAJ-Conceptualized this article. AAJ, ATA, USE, AJ, MUK, SA, ZAA, DES, SEA, WMR, SKR were involved in the design, acquisition of data, analysis, and interpretation of data. SEA performed the surgery and followed up with the patient. AAJ, ATA, USE, AJ, MUK, SA, ZAA, DES, SEA, WMR, SKR participated in the writing, editing, and revising of the article and the final version.

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Key Messages

What is already known about ovarian pregnancy?

Primary ovarian pregnancy is quite rare worldwide, and when it occurs in an African setting, it is often missed.

What this study adds: This study reveals the challenging factors in the preoperative diagnosis of unruptured primary ovarian pregnancy and offers possible solutions.

How this study might influence research, practice, or policy: This study provides guides and

conscious efforts to raise suspicions where the site of embryo implantation has not been localised.

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